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Research Article

**THE PATIENT WITH THE TYPE 2 DIABETES INCREASES
THE CHANCES OF CORONA VIRUS IN MAYO HOSPITAL
LAHORE**¹Dr Sibgha Ahmed, ²Aneza Rafaqat, ²Muhammad Hammad Joya¹Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore, ²Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Covid 19 and the type 2 diabetes are the most spreading diseases in the world about 12 million people died due to the type 2 diabetes in the world. So you can take the result from this that how it takes the lives of human what is this disease and how it takes the lives of millions of the human. In type 2 diabetes patient have the higher level of sugar and the glucose level of the body very high. We observed this in previous studies that how the human level of sugar and the glucose level in the human we also observed that the we performed the different studies on the mices and also the hc subjects. It is observed that the hc patients are those whose are have the another disease in the past. It is also observed that the patients suffering from type 2 diabetes have the lower chances of the healing. Now later the science proves that the by the insulin therapy patient can recover. Now from this sentence you must now the how the type 2 diabetes produced in the body it is due to the two main antibodies that is called the anti-gad and the anti ia2 these two antibodies when they born in the human body it starts the destruction of the beta cells. The beta cells are responsible of the observance of the insulin and insulin is responsible for the proper observance of glucose in the human body. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes exist in the insulin therapy we increases the production of beta cells so that the proper observance of insulin exist in the body and the patient starts healing. Now the covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. It is observed that the spreads through the sneezing coughing and by touching every human becomes the enemies of each other. This disease also covers the Pakistan. This question is raise in mayo hospital lahore that the patients who have the type 2 diabetes is its increase the chances of the corona virus.

Keywords: *Type 2 diabetes, Wuhan, Mayo hospital Lahore, corona virus, autoantibodies, rats.***Corresponding author:****Dr Sibgha Ahmed***Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore.*

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

In this study we have to find that the if the patient have the type 2 diabetes is his bodies starts the chances of gaining the more corona virus. This study is challenging for the mayo hospital Lahore that how they performed the study of this type in which it reveals. It is observed that the it covers the 160 countries of the world you take the result from it how it spreads in the disease. How the type 2 diabetes produced in the body it is due to the two main antibodies that is called the anti-gad and the anti ia2 these two antibodies when they born in the human body it starts the destruction of the beta cells. The beta cells are responsible of the observance of the insulin and insulin is responsible for the proper observance of glucose in the human body. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes produces in the body. The covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. These both diseases are the life taking diseases it's a challenge for the mayo hospital Lahore to find these challenge they performed a study on the patient it is observed that the 32 percent of the total survivors have the type 2 diabetes. It is observed that the how these study performed we have the files of different patient in this regard we collected the data and sorted it out according to the sex male and have the details of type 2 diabetes is he have the crucial disease before or not it is the great step.

METHODOLOGY:

We performed a study in the mayo hospital Lahore according to which patient have the type 2 diabetes it is also observed that the we performed a study on the patient in which patients have the full file of the previous studies it is observes in this study that the patient who are heal from the corona virus have 32 percent have the type 2 diabetes. From second studies it is observed that the patient does not have the diabetes had the 16 percent one of them died due to this. It is observed that the deaths in the patient have the third or fourth time the people have the chances of the death. This is a great step of the mayo hospital Lahore. It is observed that the corona virus does not take part in the type 2 patients.

RESULTS:

We have the data of the different patients in the mayo hospital Lahore. this study improves by the mayo hospital Lahore. It is observes in this study that the patient who are heal from the corona virus have 32 percent have the type 2 diabetes. From second studies it is observed that the patient does not have the

diabetes had the 16 percent one of them died due to this. It is observed that the deaths in the patient have the third or fourth time the people have the chances of the death.

DISCUSSION:

It is also observed that the patients suffering from type 2 diabetes have the lower chances of the healing. Now later the science proves that the by the insulin therapy patient can recover. Now from this sentence you must now the how the type 2 diabetes produced in the body it is due to the two main antibodies that is called the anti-gad and the anti ia2 these two antibodies when they born in the human body it starts the destruction of the beta cells. The beta cells are responsible of the observance of the insulin and insulin is responsible for the proper observance of glucose in the human body. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes exist in the insulin therapy we increases the production of beta cells so that the proper observance of insulin exist in the body and the patient starts healing. Now the covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes produces in the body. The covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. These both diseases are the life taking diseases it's a challenge for the mayo hospital Lahore to find these challenge they performed a study on the patient it is observed that the 32 percent of the total survivors have the type 2 diabetes. It is observed that the how these study performed we have the files of different patient in this regard we collected the data and sorted it out according to the sex male and have the details of type 2 diabetes is he have the crucial disease before or not it is the great step.

CONCLUSION:

This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. These both diseases are the life taking diseases it's a challenge for the mayo hospital Lahore to find these challenge they performed a study on the patient it is observed that the 32 percent of the total survivors have the type 2 diabetes. It is observed that the how these study performed we have the files of different patient in this regard we collected the data and sorted it out according to the sex male and have the details of type 2 diabetes is he have the crucial disease before or not it is the great step. From second studies it is observed that the patient does not have the

diabetes had the 16 percent one of them died due to this. It is observed that the deaths in the patient have the third or fourth time the people have the chances of the death. It is observed that the patient have the type 2 diabetes does not have the more chances of deaths it is observed that double or triple deaths to those patient which do not have the type 2 diabetes. This study does this proves. It is also observed that the patients suffering from type 2 diabetes have the lower chances of the healing. Now later the science proves that the by the insulin therapy patient can recover. Now from this sentence you must now the how the type 2 diabetes produced in the body it is due to the two main antibodies that is called the anti-gad and the anti ia2 these two antibodies when they born in the human body it starts the destruction of the beta cells. The beta cells are responsible of the observance of the insulin and insulin is responsible for the proper observance of glucose in the human body. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes exist in the insulin therapy we increases the production of beta cells so that the proper observance of insulin exist in the body and the patient starts healing.

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